

THE ROLE OF INSURANCE IN PROVIDING SERVICES TO FOREIGN TOURISTS TO UZBEKISTAN.

Samarkand Institute of Economics and Services
Ayubov Ilyas Ilkhomovich, associate professor
of the Department of "Economic Theory"

Abstract: this publication includes how the insurance company concludes contracts with insurance companies specializing in the support of foreign tourists and the procedure for direct reimbursement of expenses caused by an insurance event.

Key words: insurance policy, tour operator, compensation.

Foreign tourists, of course, are often aware of the need for insurance, as well as how much they can pay out-of-pocket for hospital services. Those who arrange their trip through tour operators do not think about health insurance, as standard tour packages must include a medical insurance policy for traveling abroad.

An extended insurance package addresses a number of potential issues. Insurance in case of trip cancellation; compensation for losses in case of flight delay; reimbursement of expenses in the event of an accident; including civil liability insurance. Foreign tourists buy insurance from a selection of companies accepted by all visa centers and with round-the-clock support. This not only creates favorable conditions, but also helps in attracting foreign tourists.

Traditionally, "travel insurance" is understood as a policy that entitles foreign tourists to receive necessary medical care in the host country. The medical insurance policy is an auxiliary document and its content is ignored and it is completely useless - medical insurance is necessary during the trip and other types of foreign tourist insurance help to prevent other serious problems during the trip.

However, responsible tourists who prefer to travel independently, as well as those who go on frequent business trips, know the need for travel medical insurance and buy insurance policies themselves, usually online booking on the website of insurance companies they do. Practice shows that those who have encountered similar problems at least once during a trip will buy insurance when traveling abroad in the future.

At the same time, in addition to the standard health insurance, you can protect yourself in other unexpected situations. For this purpose, for example, baggage loss insurance, travel ban protection and many other options are provided. A risk protection policy for those traveling abroad is not the only way to protect yourself while traveling, along with classic health insurance. insurance, it may include other types of risks.

These can include: medical expenses - as mentioned above, this type of insurance is necessary for foreign tourists traveling abroad. Even if we talk about visa-free countries, health insurance is usually included in the package of entry documents. The sum insured for such insurance includes the medicines prescribed by the doctor.

For this, you need to call the contact number of the insurance company. The costs of hospital treatment, transport of the victim to the hospital or place of residence or stay in the hospital are specified in the insurance contract. The insurance company, or rather, its partner in each country, has arranged the arrival of an ambulance or other means of transport.

If a person cannot fly home in time due to the need for hospital treatment, the insured event for this type of insurance is a sudden illness within the scope of the insurance. In this case, the event is not considered insured if it is related to chronic diseases known at the time of conclusion of the insurance contract or diseases that the insured person had previously. There is a certain logic in this, because the essence of insurance is to protect against risks, the occurrence of which is difficult to predict.

If a person with a heart condition goes on vacation to another country, the responsibility for their own health should lie with them, not with the insurance company. If a healthy person has a heart problem, the insurer covers the costs of necessary diagnostics, medicines prescribed by the doctor and hospitalization. In addition, if the insured person misses the flight due to hospitalization, the insurance company arranges and pays for his return to the place of permanent residence (all expenses are covered within the sum insured specified in the insurance contract).

The standard amount of medical insurance for most countries (including Central Asian countries) is 5,000 euros (the cost of such travel insurance can be from 0.5 to 1 euro per day's stay); Except for America, Canada, Japan, where the amount of TZR insurance coverage must be at least 50,000 USD. The price of insurance for these countries is slightly more expensive.

In this case, the insurer has the right to involve independent experts to determine the actual damage, based on which the insurance payment is made. In this case, an unconditional deduction of 10% of the amount of damage is usually applied. However, you can insure your cargo for any amount that will be reimbursed to you under the terms of the insurance contract. In other cases, there are usually limits on damages for a particular risk. The price of such insurance varies between 2-20 US dollars. Travel up to 30 days is insured depending on the insurance amount.

Accident insurance is a type of voluntary foreign tourist insurance (as opposed to mandatory health insurance, for example) that covers injury or disability as a result of an accident.

Data processing is carried out on a secure high-tech server of the company. Credit card information is transmitted encrypted and is not stored on a web server. All entered personal data of customers is stored on a secure server, only company specialists have access to the data.

List of used literature:

1. Кизим А.А., Вальвашов А.Н., Кулькова И.В. Повышение инвестиционной привлекательности туристических региона на основе

развития туристического кластера // Туристических региональная экономика: теория и практика. – 2010. – № 26 (161). – С. 52-59.;

2. Коль О.Д. Концептуальные основы формирования кластера туристских предпринимательских структур по въездному туризму в крупном городе // Проблемы современной экономики. – 2010. – № 1 (33). – С. 379-383.;

3. Воронов, А. Кластерный анализ – база управления конкурентоспособностью на макроуровне / А. Воронов, А. Буряк // Маркетинг. 2003. № 1(68). С. 16.

4. Д.А. Пятина. Концептуальные подходы к кластеризации в сфере туризма. // Региональные исследования. 2008. - № 5 (20). - С. 51-56.